

ID	Architectural Decision	Implementation Layers	Challenges ID	Source	Description	Rationale
AD1	Identify distributed data processing and transmission component according to the stakeholders needs (use case)	All	CH1, CH4, CH5, CH6, CH7, CH8 CH9	Domain-Knowledge	Parametrized decision according to operational scenario desired to be achieved. Balance between volume of data to be sent, power consumption and impact of transmission. Processing of data must be done accordingly.	Tradeoff between energy efficiency, data availability and volume (compression), network security solutions' data - reconstruct information if needed" - reduce impact on the environment. In some cases the data acquisition system should have the possibility to send only "data diffs" (changes in data) - missing raw data.
AD2	Data Platform	Layers 2 and 3	CH12	Implementation	Intermediary component between data producing and data consumer systems. Responsible for data management at cloud level.	Layer that is responsible for data processing pipeline and storage - external data provider in the arch reflects the fusion component needs.
AD3	Data Processing Services: Ingestion Messaging Service (Message Oriented)	Layers 2 and 3	CH1, CH2, CH9	Domain-Knowledge	Message-oriented following the publish-subscribe pattern for data ingestion into data platform. Standardize the delivery of heterogenous data and data delivery methods.	Data Providers don't have knowledge on who is going to consume the data (data publishes on topics). Separate access to data. Challenges on data management. Loose Coupling. Sparse data over time (low volume of data ingested wirelessly). Automate ocean data stream (push base) migrating from data delivery via (s/ftp or REST APIs (pull based).
AD4	MQTT Protocol	Layers 2 and 3	CH4, CH7, CH9	Software Technologies	Adoption of the MQTT IoT lowfootprint communication protocol for the message oriented data ingestion.	After analysing the size of data the choose was to use MQTT. Low bandwidth - Acoustic Communication - After analysing the size of data the choose was to use MQTT. QoS levels - configurable. 2 ways communication. Missing Raw data - sending only alarms.
AD4.1	Migration to data delivery using MQTT - company 1	Layers 2 and 3		Implementation	Consequence of decisions AD3 and AD4.	Consequence of decisions AD3 and AD4
AD4.2	Migration to data delivery using MQTT - company 2	Layers 2 and 3		Implementation	Consequence of decisions AD3 and AD4.	Consequence of decisions AD3 and AD4
AD5	Platform Monitoring Service and Data Processing Services: Data Validation	Layer 3	CH1, CH2, CH4, CH12, CH13, CH15	Domain-Knowledge	Components instrumentation to detect faults throughout the data processing pipeline but also from the data acquisition and network layers. Instrumentation data can also be used for root cause analysis of faults providing contextual information.	Check ingestion data for currentness, volume, and schema violations (inconsistency). Network Communication Challenges (Unreliable Data Transmission & Battery consumption). Another main driver is the unreliability of the Underwater Wireless Sensor Network.
AD6	Data Processing Services: Data QC	Layer 3	CH5, CH11, CH12	Domain-Knowledge	Data quality control component to detect the level of adequacy of data according to different dimensions.	Data quality is one of the main drivers and concern from all stakeholders across the different organizations. Trust factor to use the data for decision making. QC is related to the use case of data (usability)
AD7	Data Model	Layers 1 and 3	CH3, CH10, CH12	Domain-Knowledge	Unifying data and metadata model for heterogenous data sources.	Simplify the SOA implications of dealing with many data formats fostering an unified representation and semantics at the layers processing heterogenous data. Model expected to evolve keeping backwards compatibility.
AD7.1	Data Processing Services: Data Transformation	Layer 3		Implementation	Consequence of the decision "data model" (AD7).	Responsible for the validation and conversion of ingested data into the data platform internal data model.
AD7.2	Separation of Ingestion and Services Brokers	Layer 3		Implementation	Consequence of the decision "data model" (AD7).	Entrypoint from ingestion brokers and the services broker (deal with data loss and unavailability in the ingestion broker side. Data stream processing - decoupled services in the pipeline for elasticity because of scarce and intervaled data ingestion (scalable).
AD8	identity provider	Layers 2 and 3	CH13, CH15	Implementation	Authentication and authorization management.	There are already solutions above water (ex: JWT integration in HiveMQ), the challenge comes from the authentication inside the underwater wireless sensor network (no solution - current open problem).
AD9	Data Sharing: Access Control	Layer 3	CH13, CH14, CH15	Domain-Knowledge	Management of access to the data stream.	Data "Vecting" or release control based authorization according to data category, type or other available attributes.
AD10	Data Sharing: Configuration of data that is shared and Data Classification	Layer 3	CH13, CH14	Domain-Knowledge	Filter different types of data impacting the access control to data shared on the data consumer application side.	Depends on the granularity of data access control and available metadata. Challenges on data management related to data reusability.
AD10.1	Added REST API for end user application side	Layer 3		Software Technologies	Consequence of data sharing in general.	Implementation of pull method for data retrieval by data consumer applications complying to services communication common practices.